

The Imitator: Severe Aortic Stenosis Masquerading as an Acute Coronary Syndrome

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INTRODUCTION

The Clinical presentation of acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is very vast , it can go from acute chest pain to hemodynamic instability with cardiogenic shock or cardiac arrest .

The most frequent symptom is acute chest discomfort described as chest pain , pressure , tightness and burning with some symptoms equivalent such as dyspnea , epigastric pain , or pain in the left arm .(1)

ACS defines a necrosis of cardiomyocytes with acute ischemia , that can be caused by occlusion of coronary arteries but it's not always the case : aortic stenosis (AS) can lead to inadequate perfusion of the myocardium without any demonstrable coronary stenosis or occlusion .

AS occurs in 2-9 % of the general population over the age of 65 and shares ACS risk factors.(2)

Left ventricular systolic dysfunction and heart failure (HF) in AS is a predictor of poor outcome even after valve replacement.(3)

HF in AS comes after structural and functional changes of the heart with left ventricular hypertrophy that will lead to degeneration and death of cardiac myocytes .(4)

We present the case report of 69 years old patient with severe AS and a clinical presentation masquerading as an ACS .

CASE REPORT

A 69 year-old woman with morbid obesity , and a previous medical history of uncontrolled diabetes ,hypertension and dyslipidemia , referred to our ER Hospital for a typical ACS chest pain , that lasted 3 hours before arrival .Physical examination revealed a systolic ejection murmur and an absent S2 heart sound in the aortic area .

Electrocardiography examination showed a ST segment elevation in anterior leads .(Figure 1)

Given the ECG findings, she was immediately admitted to the cath lab for coronary angiography and percutaneous coronary intervention (PPCI).

Figure 1:ECG when arriving at the ER.

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Coronary angiography was normal.(Figure 2,3,4).

Figure 1,2 : Normal Coronary angiography of the left coronary artery ,

Figure 3: Normal Coronary angiography of the Right coronary artery

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After that a bedside echocardiography was performed , showing important calcification of the aortic and mitral valve using 2D echocardiography (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Calcifications on the mitral and aortic valve.

And severe aortic stenosis qualitative criteria : Vmax : 4 m/s , Mean PG 40 mmhg , AVA (VTI) 0.8 cm² and indexed AVA at 0.34 cm²/m² .(Figure 5)

Figure 5 : Severe aortic stenosis criteria.

A normal planimetry mitral valve area (MVA) .(Figure 6)

Figure 6 : Normal mitral valve area.

And important calcifications of the ascending aorta in the suprasternal view .(Figure 7)

Figure 7: Important calcifications of the ascending aorta.

Prior to coronary angiography , the patient was given loading dose of aspirin and clopidogrel .

After the identification of critical AS by echocardiography , antiplatelet therapy was discontinued and the patient was transferred to the intensive cardiac care unit (ICCU) for further treatment given the clinical and electrocardiography presentation of ACS without evidence of coronary occlusion nor stenosis .The case was discussed with our heart team and the patient was planned for urgent AV replacement .

DISCUSSION

Left compensatory left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) caused by severe aortic stenosis can cause a decrease in the coronary vasodilator reserve (CVR) which increase the ratio between maximal and basal coronary blood flow .

CVR is usable as a functional index of coronary artery insufficiency severity even in cases of normal coronary arteries.(5)

CVR decrease is also described in cases of hypertrophic and hypertensive cardiomyopathy.(6)

In patients with decreased CVR, diastolic perfusion time (DPT) have an important effect on it as an increase of the heart rate, will significantly decrease the CVR .(7)

This case scenario can happen in critical aortic stenosis causing a significant impair of subendocardial perfusion thus ischemia.

Studies have showed that there is no clear relationship between the degree of LVH and CVR but on the other hand the interaction of both DPT and valve area seems to be a significant risk factor of ischemia in aortic stenosis. (8)

In cases like the one that we report of critical aortic stenosis presenting as an acute coronary syndrome.

A good physical examination is crucial to establish the diagnosis among other tests such as ECG, Echocardiography and Laboratory tests.

The aortic stenosis murmur is a systolic murmur that begins after a gap corresponding to the period of isovolumetric contraction of the left ventricle.

Afterward the murmur becomes intense due to the increase of blood flow through the aortic valve during increase of left ventricular pressure resulting in a crescendo murmur then the forward flow decreases and the intensity of the murmur too which leads to a decrescendo murmur.

The intensity of the murmur Isn't correlated to the severity of aortic stenosis but more severe is the stenosis, the longer it will take to force blood through the valve so the peak of the systolic murmur will be delayed as a result.

The aortic component S2 will progressively decrease as the valve becomes more rigid.

Another common findings on cardiac examination of severe aortic stenosis is the presence of S4 due to “stiff” atrial-LV contractions.(9)

ST segment elevation most often occurs in type 1 acute myocardial infarction.

But can be due to other cardiac or extracardiac conditions such as spontaneous coronary artery dissection , pericarditis,myocarditis,Aorticdissection,pneumonia ,hyperkalemia, thyroid storm ... (10)

In the case that we report, the ST segment elevation in the anterior leads plus the typical chest pain complaints caused

the suspicion of ACS as the first diagnosis when the patient presented to the ER.

The trans-thoracic Echocardiography (TTE) is a more sensitive test to assess ventricular wall thickness and excursion of the stenotic valve.

Beside the transvalvular pressure gradient and aortic valve area can be calculated very easily with Doppler. (11)

In this case the TTE results were compatible with aortic stenosis and not with acute coronary syndrome: narrowed aortic valve area, high transgradient pressure, highly calcified aortic valve with left ventricular hypertrophy and no regional wall abnormalities.

Cardiac troponin I (cTnI) is detected in more than half of the patients and is elevated in more than one fifth of patients with severe aortic stenosis.

But extreme increase of troponin is rare in the absence of acute coronary syndrome.

The reason behind the extreme elevation in cardiac biomarkers in patients with critical aortic stenosis is still to be determined but could be associated with decreased vasodilator reserve and diastolic perfusion time.

This cardiac biomarker may be elevated even in the absence of systolic dysfunction indicating that positive cTnI may precede LV dysfunction.

Therefore cTnI monitoring can be helpful to identify the onset of the inevitable clinical decline in severe aortic stenosis.(12)

CONCLUSION

Although acute coronary syndrome is the most common and most fatal cause of repolarization abnormalities, other causes must be considered and ruled out through a thorough clinical examination, a well performed transthoracic echocardiogram and appropriate cardiac biomarkers.

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